

Impact of Research Publications of Bhatnagar Awardees in Biological Sciences (2011-20): An Evaluation through Traditional Vis-À-Vis Alternative Metrics

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Abstract: This study evaluates the research publications of Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar (SSB) awardees in biological sciences through a multidimensional analysis of publication metrics. Using bibliometric data from Scopus, Mendeley, and Altmetrics platforms, 1,054 publications across 18 laureates spanning 2011–2020 have been analysed to assess productivity (article counts), academic influence (citations, readership), and societal engagement (Altmetric Attention Scores). This study reveals that publication productivity does not consistently correlate with long-term impact, Mendeley readership strongly aligns with citation counts, and altmetric attention shows significant variability independent of traditional metrics, highlighting the complex nature of research evaluation in biological sciences.

Keywords: Bhatnagar awardees, Research Impact Assessment, Bibliometrics, Altmetrics, Citation Analysis, Mendeley Readership, Scientific Productivity, Biological Sciences.

1 Introduction

Biological science, a cornerstone of the natural sciences, is the systematic study of living organisms and their interactions with the environment, encompassing diverse sub-disciplines such as molecular biology, genetics, ecology, and physiology. (Alberts et al., 2022) Research in biological science unravels the complexities of life, from the molecular mechanisms driving cellular processes to the intricate dynamics of ecosystems, thereby advancing medical, agricultural, and environmental innovations. (National Research Council, 2009) The impact of biological research on society has been profound, catalysing breakthroughs such as vaccines, genetic engineering, and biodiversity conservation while also addressing global challenges. (Collins & Varmus, 2015) Evaluating research output in this field helps assess its impact and influence on future researchers and society, leading to

tangible real-world contributions. (Bornmann et al., 2012)

To comprehensively evaluate the research output of a given subject area, it is essential to prioritize scholarly articles and publications that have demonstrated significant influence within the field. This influence can be measured through high citation counts, publication in high-impact journals, or the inclusion of works by distinguished authors whose contributions have been widely recognized (Bornmann et al., 2012). Established researchers often achieve prominence through groundbreaking discoveries, sustained academic impact, or prestigious accolades such as Nobel Prizes, Lasker Awards, or other discipline-specific honours, which further validate the credibility of their work (Bjørk, 2020). By focusing on such high-impact publications—those occupying the upper tiers of academic influence researchers can ensure a robust and representative analysis of the field's intellectual progress (Hicks et al., 2015). A systematic examination of top-tier research outputs not only enhances the rigor of academic evaluation but also helps identify key trends, knowledge gaps, and future directions within the discipline (National Research Council, 2009).

For this study, the research output of Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar (SSB) Prize awardees in Biological Sciences has been selected for evaluation, as their contributions represent the pinnacle of scientific excellence in India. Instituted in 1958 by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), the SSB Prize is India's most prestigious scientific honour, named after Dr. Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar, the founder director of CSIR. The prize is conferred annually for exceptional research and outstanding contributions to science and technology, spanning seven disciplines, including Biological Sciences.

In the domain of Biological Sciences, Bhatnagar laureates have made transformative discoveries, significantly shaping both national and global research landscapes. By analysing the works of these distinguished scientists, this study not only tracks the development of advanced biological research in India but also underscores the role of elite recognition systems in identifying and validating groundbreaking contributions to science.

This study employs a dual methodological approach, integrating traditional bibliometric metrics and altmetric measures to comprehensively evaluate the research publications of Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences. Traditional metrics quantify academic influence, revealing patterns in scholarly impact through citation analysis and journal prestige. Complementing these, altmetrics track non-traditional indicators such as online attention, policy citations, and patent references providing insights into the broader societal engagement and real-world dissemination of their work.

2 Objectives of the Study

This study aims to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the research output of Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences. The specific objectives are:

- i. To examine year-wise publication trends, citation patterns, and social visibility metrics to identify temporal variations in research productivity and impact in biological sciences.
- ii. To assess the research impact of each awardee by employing both traditional indicators and alternative metrics (altmetrics) that capture broader societal engagement in biological sciences.
- iii. To perform a detailed analysis of altmetric components to evaluate their societal influence.
- iv. To investigate whether the impact factor of journals correlates with the publication frequency of the awardees, thereby exploring the influence of journal prestige on research output.

3 Scope

This study evaluates the scholarly impact of Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences, focusing exclusively on researchers awarded between 2011-2020. The analysis is restricted to 1,054 Scopus-indexed articles published by the 18 selected awardees during this decade. To maintain analytical focus on high-impact research, only the 100 most-cited articles per awardee (where applicable) were included in the evaluation.

4 Methodology

This study employs a dual-metric analytical approach, combining traditional bibliometric indicators and alternative metrics (altmetrics) to comprehensively evaluate the research impact of research publications by Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences. The analysis focuses on journal articles and review papers published by these distinguished researchers, awarded between 2011 and 2020, with all data systematically retrieved from the Scopus database in January 2025.

The research methodology followed a rigorous multi-stage process. First, Scopus author profiles of each awardee were identified, from which all articles and review articles published in a journal through 2024 were extracted using Scopus's advanced filtering system. To ensure analytical focus on high-impact research, a maximum of 100 most-cited articles were selected for each prolific author (those with >100 publications), yielding a final dataset of 1,054 articles published by the 18 awardees. For each article, traditional citation metrics from Scopus alongside altmetric indicators including Mendeley reader counts, Altmetric Attention Scores (AAS), and detailed social media mentions across multiple platforms were retrieved using the Altmetric bookmarklet tool and the altmetric.org details page, which provides granular data on social media mentions and their contribution to the overall AAS.

To assess the relationship between journal prestige and publication frequency, the top 10 journals with the highest number of publications in the dataset were identified. Their Impact Factors (IF) were sourced from official journal websites and analysed to determine whether IF correlates with the volume of publications by awardees.

Throughout the study, all references and citations adhere to the American Psychological Association (APA) 6th edition style guidelines to maintain academic rigor and consistency in documentation.

5 Data Analysis

Scopus citations measure academic influence by tracking how often research is cited in scholarly literature. Mendeley readership reflects early researcher engagement and often precedes future citations. The Altmetric Attention Score (AAS) assesses broader societal impact by monitoring mentions in news, social media, policy documents, and patents, extending beyond traditional academic recognition.

Figure 1: Temporal Analysis of Research Productivity and Impact Metrics in Biological Sciences

Figure 1 presents aggregated data on the total Scopus citations, Mendeley readers, and AAS per article for each year range. Due to significant inconsistencies in the raw values, the figure displays averaged values relative to the total number of articles published in the respective year ranges. It reveals clear trends in publication output and research influence across five-year intervals. The 2015-2019 period marks the highest productivity with 272 publications, while the most recent phase (2020-2024) follows with 194 articles. Earlier periods demonstrate a steady decrease in output. In terms of Scopus citations, the 2005-2009 interval has the strongest impact, averaging 136.82 citations, trailed by 2000-2004 with 86.57. Conversely, the latest period (2020-2024) records the lowest average citations at 18.97. A similar pattern emerges in Mendeley readership, where 2005-2009 leads with 122.64 average readers, and 2015-2019 follows with 88.46, while recent works attract fewer readers. Notably, Altmetric attention scores peak in the 2020-2024 period, averaging 16.54, before dropping significantly in earlier years and disappearing entirely for works from 1994 and before.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Traditional and Alternative Metrics in Assessing Research Impact among Bhatnagar Awardees in Biological Sciences

Sl. No.	Author name (awarded in year)	Total Number of articles	Total Scopus citations	Total Mendeley readers	Total AAS
1	Dr. Subhadeep Chatterjee (2020)	34	1610	2191	131
2	Dr. Vatsala Thirumalai (2020)	26	972	1585	255

Sl. No.	Author name (awarded in year)	Total Number of articles	Total Scopus citations	Total Mendeley readers	Total AAS
3	Dr. Soumen Basak (2019)	40	1778	2349	179
4	Dr. Kayarat Saikrishnan (2019)	19	422	666	56
5	Dr. Ganesh Nagaraju (2018)	33	1381	1894	96
6	Dr. Thomas Pucadyil (2018)	57	3390	3722	391
7	Dr. Deepak Thankappan Nair (2017)	50	1881	1863	404
8	Dr. Sanjeev Das (2017)	27	1050	1090	53
9	Dr. Rishikesh Narayanan (2016)	57	1528	2547	233
10	Dr. Suvendra Nath Bhattacharyya (2016)	41	9778	8761	450
11	Dr. Balasubramanian Gopal (2015)	88	1319	2213	206
12	Dr. Rajeev Kumar Varshney (2015)	100	29362	29587	3726
13	Dr. Roop Mallik (2014)	57	2816	3014	322
14	Dr. Sathees Chukkurumbal Raghavan (2013)	100	5787	6155	313
15	Dr. Shantanu Chowdhury (2012)	61	2795	3738	213
16	Dr. Suman Kumar Dhar (2012)	71	2772	2738	193
17	Dr. Amit Prakash Sharma (2011)	93	3086	4558	1271
18	Dr. Rajan Sankaranarayanan (2011)	100	3024	3383	332
Total		1054	74751	82054	8824

Table 1 presents the publication records and impact measures (Scopus citations, Mendeley readership, and Altmetric Attention Scores) for 18 Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences. Collectively, these awardees have published 1,054 articles accumulating 74,751 citations and 82,054 Mendeley readers, with a combined Altmetric Attention Score of 8,824. The data reveals considerable variation in publication output, ranging from 19 to 100 articles per researcher. Dr. Rajeev Kumar Varshney emerges as the top performer across all metrics, leading in total publications (100 articles), Scopus citations (29,362), Mendeley readership (29,587), and AAS (3,726). Following closely, Dr. Suvendra Nath Bhattacharyya demonstrates strong academic impact with the second-highest citations (9,778) and readership (8,761), though with comparatively lower AAS (450) despite having fewer

publications (41 articles). Notably, Dr. Sathees Chukkurumbal Raghavan shares the highest publication count (100 articles) but shows moderate citation (5,787) and readership numbers (6,155), along with relatively low AAS (313). An interesting pattern appears when comparing Dr. Amit Prakash Sharma (93 publications, 3,086 citations, 4,558 readers, 1,271 AAS) and Dr. Thomas Pucadyil (57 publications, 3,390 citations, 3,722 readers, 391 AAS), where similar citation counts accompany markedly different AAS values. The AAS metric displays particularly wide variability, ranging from as low as 53 to as high as 3,726.

Table 2: Altmetric Components and their Societal Influence in Biological Sciences Research

Components	Total number of attentions in biological sciences	Percentage
Twitter/X	6848	79.44
Patent	477	5.53
Wikipedia	372	4.32
News	343	3.98
Facebook	301	3.49
Blog	94	1.09
Policy document	57	0.66
Research highlight platform	48	0.56
Google+ users	37	0.43
YouTube	16	0.19
Peer reviews	13	0.15
Reddit	12	0.14
Q&A forums	2	0.02

The Altmetric Attention Score (AAS) is calculated by tracking mentions across various online platforms, where each component contributes differently based on predefined weightings assigned by Altmetric. For every mention in a platform, a predetermined score is assigned according to Altmetrics weighting system, and the sum of all these individual platform scores constitutes the final AAS. Table 2 presents the distribution of total number mentions across 13 tracked platforms for 1,054 publications by 18 Bhatnagar Awardees in biological sciences. Twitter emerges as the overwhelmingly dominant platform, accounting for 6,848 mentions (79.44% of total attention). Other significant components include patent citations (477 mentions, 5.53%), Wikipedia (372 mentions, 4.32%), and news outlets (343 mentions, 3.98%). In contrast, several platforms show minimal engagement, with YouTube (16 mentions, 0.19%), peer reviews (13 mentions, 0.15%), Reddit (12 mentions, 0.14%), and Q&A forums (2 mentions, 0.02%) representing the least active components.

The impact factor (IF) has long served as a key metric of journal prestige, influencing academic reputation and career advancement. This study analyses the publication distribution of top biological sciences researchers across journals, exploring the relationship between journal impact factor and publication frequency to understand current trends in elite research dissemination.

Table 3: Analysis of Journal Publication Patterns and Impact Factor Influence in Biological Sciences Research

Sl. No.	Top 10 journals by publication frequency	Total number of articles	Impact Factor in 2023
1	Journal Of Biological Chemistry	46	4
2	Nucleic Acids Research	46	16.7
3	Scientific Reports	29	3.8
4	Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America	25	9.4
5	Acta Crystallographica Section D Biological Crystallography	22	2.6
6	Biochemistry	21	2.9
7	Journal Of Molecular Biology	21	4.7
8	Plos One	21	2.9
9	FEBS Journal	17	5.5
10	Acta Crystallographica Section F Structural Biology and Crystallization Communication	15	1.1

The top 10 journals where the highest number of articles by Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences were published are listed in Table 3. The Journal of Biological Chemistry and Nucleic Acids Research were found to have the highest number of publications, with 46 articles each, despite their significantly different Impact Factors (4 and 16.7, respectively). Scientific Reports and Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America (PNAS) were observed to have the second-highest number of publications, with 29 and 25 articles, respectively, though their Impact Factors (3.8 and 9.4) differed considerably. The next four journals Acta Crystallographica Section D Biological Crystallography, Biochemistry, Journal of Molecular Biology, and Plos One were noted to have a similar number of publications (ranging from 22 to 21 articles), with relatively close Impact Factors (2.6, 2.9, 4.7, and 2.9, respectively). The lowest number of publications among the top 10 journals were recorded in FEBS Journal (17 articles, Impact Factor 5.5) and Acta Crystallographica Section F Structural Biology and Crystallization Communications (15 articles, Impact Factor 1.1).

6 Findings

- I. The data in Figure 1 shows that in recent years, the number of publications has been higher compared to earlier years among the Bhatnagar Awardees in Biological Sciences. This suggests that research output has increased over time within this group. When examining citation and

readership patterns, Scopus and Mendeley show similar trends—articles with higher average readership on Mendeley also tend to have higher average citations. This indicates that readership could be a useful predictor of future citations, as articles that attract more readers are likely to accumulate more citations over time.

However, there is a notable difference when looking at Altmetric Attention Score (AAS). Unlike citations and Mendeley readership, which grow steadily over time, the AAS drops sharply for older articles. At the same time, newer articles tend to have higher AAS values. This reinforces the idea that AAS is more relevant as a short-term impact metric, reflecting changes in how research is shared and recognized. The trend suggests that modern research dissemination practices may prioritize quick visibility and online engagement over the slower, citation-based measures of long-term impact.

- II. The table 1 shows that the publication quantity (ranging from 19 to 100 articles per researcher) does not consistently correlate with academic impact, as some authors with moderate publication numbers achieved higher citation counts than those with more publications.

Mendeley readership (82,054 total) consistently parallels Scopus citation patterns (74,751 total) across all researchers, regardless of their publication volume. This close alignment suggests these metrics provide complementary measures of scholarly impact. Notably, Mendeley readership exceeds total citations by approximately 9.8%, indicating broader early-stage engagement than formal citation counts capture.

The Altmetric Attention Scores (total 8,824) demonstrate markedly different behaviour, being significantly lower than both citation and readership metrics. These scores fluctuate independently of traditional impact measures, with values ranging widely from 53 to 3,726 regardless of publication numbers or citation counts. This pattern shows unlike citation-based metrics, AAS solely indicates how widely research is shared and discussed in public forums and social media which are tracked by altmetrics.

- III. The data reveal a striking dominance of Twitter in research dissemination, comprising 79.44% (6,848 mentions) of all altmetric attention. While Facebook (3.49%), Wikipedia (4.32%), and news outlets (3.98%) show moderate engagement.

The overwhelming focus on social media engagement (especially Twitter) in altmetric scores suggests these metrics capture public visibility more effectively than academic recognition. This pattern likely occurs because: traditional academic platforms like peer reviews and research highlights are either less visible to the public or less actively discussed online; researchers may still prefer conventional academic channels over social media for sharing their work; and/or these scholarly platforms simply receive less public attention compared to mainstream social media. While Altmetric can technically track all these platforms, the low engagement in traditional academic platforms peer reviews (0.15%), research highlights (0.56%), and Q&A forums (0.02%) collectively account for less than 1% of total mentions, indicates either limited public interest in these formats or researchers' continued reliance on traditional dissemination methods. This reveals an important limitation of AAS it measures what is popular in online public discourse rather than comprehensive academic impact.

- IV. Based on the data presented in Table 3, it is observed that the selection of journals for publishing articles by Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences is not solely determined by the Impact

Factor (IF) of the journals. Instead, other factors—such as the scope of the journal, target audience, or relevance to the discipline—appear to be prioritized by researchers when choosing publication venues.

7 Conclusion

This study comprehensively evaluates the research impact of Bhatnagar awardees in biological sciences, integrating traditional bibliometrics (citations, Mendeley readership) and altmetrics (AAS, social media, patents, policy citations) to reveal key patterns in scientific influence. The findings demonstrate that while citations reflect long-term academic impact, AAS captures short-term visibility, and Mendeley readership strongly correlates with scholarly recognition. Notably, peak publication output in recent years contrasts with the sustained influence of earlier research, highlighting that productivity alone does not guarantee long-term impact. Social media, particularly Twitter, dominates research dissemination, whereas patent and policy citations underscore significant societal and industrial engagement. The study also reveals that journal selection is influenced by disciplinary relevance and accessibility rather than impact factor alone. These insights advocate for a balanced, multidimensional framework for research assessment—one that values academic, societal, and economic impact. Future research should explore longitudinal altmetric trends and industry engagement to refine impact evaluation in biological sciences.

References:

- Alberts, B. et al. (2015). *Molecular Biology of the Cell* (7th ed.). New York, W. W. Norton & Company.
- Altmetric. (2024, December 3). The donut and Altmetric Attention Score - Altmetric. Retrieved from <https://www.altmetric.com/about-us/our-data/donut-and-altmetric-attention-score/>
- Bjørk, R. (2020). The journals in physics that publish Nobel Prize research. *Scientometrics*, 122(2), 817-823. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03312-8>
- Bornmann, L., de Moya-Anegón, F., & Leydesdorff, L. (2012). The new excellence indicator in the World Report of the SCImago Institutions Rankings 2011. *Journal of Informetrics*, 6(2), 333–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2011.11.006>
- Collins, F. S., & Varmus, H. (2015). A new initiative on precision medicine. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 372(9), 793–795. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp1500523>
- Council of Scientific & Industrial Research. (n.d.). Regulations governing the award of the Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize for Science and Technology. Retrieved from https://csirhrdg.res.in/SiteContent/ManagedContent/ContentFiles/20220109211426327Proforma_pdf_2022.pdf
- Hicks, D. et al. (2015). Bibliometrics: The Leiden Manifesto for research metrics. *Nature*, 520(7548), 429–431. <https://doi.org/10.1038/520429a>
- National Research Council. (2009). *A new biology for the 21st century*. Washington, National Academies Press.

- Press Information Bureau (PIB). (2021). JNCASR Scientist wins Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize for ground-breaking discoveries for treatment of Alzheimer's and lung cancer. Retrieved from <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1760791>
- Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize for Science and Technology. Council of Scientific & Industrial Research. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.csir.res.in/en/award/shanti-swarup-bhatnagar-prize-science-and-technology>
- Wikipedia contributors. (2025, April 13). Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize for Science and Technology. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shanti_Swarup_Bhatnagar_Prize_for_Science_and_Technology
- Wikipedia contributors. (2025, June 6). List of Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize recipients. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Shanti_Swarup_Bhatnagar_Prize_recipients